

BEHAVIORAL LANGUAGE ETIQUETTE IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH PROVERBS AND SAYINGS

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Annotation

This article discusses the appearance, differences similarities of speech etiquette in Uzbek languages. The article consists of an abstract on request, keywords, introduction, main body, conclusion and list of references.

Key words: affixes, accuracy, abbreviations, translation and phraseology

From ancient times, the culture of obscene moral talking about the Uzbek people is considered a very important value in the culture. In the works of our great writers, they have skillfully used the proverbs and phrases belonging to morality of moral significance.

Benevolence, great nature continuously gives individuals, bliss distinction, joy peace. "As the saying goes, A astute finds what to talk (uzb. "Dono topib gapirar")," it is in illustration of both intelligence and cordiality to precise one's thoughts in important, unpretentious words.

The incredible artist and scholar Alisher Navai considers around this and says that it is conceivable to grant a unadulterated soul to the human body with words, and bad habit versa, to crush the soul within the body with words. At the same time, in "Mahbub-ul-Qulub": Navai inclinations individuals to think gradually, to eat what comes to them is the work of an creature, and what comes to his mouth is the work of a trick. Each word of Alisher Navai around conduct features a profound meaning. There's a saying among Uzbek individuals: "Talk the truth, indeed if a sword comes to your head." To begin with of all, Navai was a staunch guard of genuineness in his time. In specific, in his epic "Hayratul-abror" he devoted a uncommon chapter on this theme, "Within the definition of Truth ...". In this case, the artist says, on the off chance that you cannot talk the truth, keep calm, but never lie:

Necha zarurat aro Qolg'on chog'I, (In case you're in need) Chin demas ersang, Dema yolg'on dog'i. (Don't tell a lie, in case you don't need to tell the truth) Misrepresentation of the truth is such a propensity that it devastates one's notoriety and condemns oneself to humiliation. Considering in all directions may be a sign of human shrewdness and insights. Navai moreover detested garbage and counter-intuitive thoughts. In one of his sermons in this epic, he says: Yana bukim yaxshi, yomon dema so`z El yomonu, yaxshisiga solma ko`z. It turns out that Navai inclinations individuals not to tune in to anyone's garbage, and at the

same time not to fault anyone. Uzbek individuals say that, "He who talks without considering kicks the bucket without pain", "Told words are shot weapon", "He who talks small could be a small off-base", "Don't say futile words as well much, never halt to listen useful words." There's a saying, "In case your words are silver, your quiet is gold." From these Uzbek sayings able to learn the taking after implications: On the off chance that you need to say something to somebody, think around it to begin with. Assume that somebody told you that. Not considering do not hurt someone's soul, at that point don't be penitent. On the off chance that you conversation without considering, you'll be humiliated and individuals will turn absent from you. It is superior to remain quiet and not express a word without cooking it in your heart.

Sympathy brings mortification and torment to a man. Since each word that comes out of one's mouth, whether it is nice or awful, whether it is suitable or improper, cannot be changed. The talked word (especially insuperable, incongruity, joke, separation, slander, gossip, boasting, bootlicking, etc.) could be a blow to the proprietor of the word (a sharp word or a physical blow) by those around him. "Words from the mouth don't return", "Speech does not go with the speaker", "Stored words are immaculate gold", "Before you say, you claim the word, after you have got said it the word will claim you", "Say what ought to be said, do not say what shouldn't be said", "Let the minor matter stay in your mouth", "If you say it, the word comes out, in the event that you touch it, the eye comes out."

When individuals contend with each other, both sides can discover the correct word suitable them. As a result, rumors can heighten into a battle. In case a individual pushes somebody (even if it's a joke), this could in the long run lead to a battle. There are society stories, legends, stories and truisms around how important it is to take after dialect behavior in managing with people. There's no apparatus that can influence a individual more than words. You'll impact somebody verbally, induce him or make him cry, make him need to live, or extinguish that energy, make him your companion or make him a match. But, tragically, not everybody pays sufficient consideration to this effective constrain of the word.

This article has appeared that in each proverb or the saying the foremost curiously social data has been concluded, over the centuries transmitted from era to era. No other dialect stores can compare with sayings and platitudes in terms of data approximately traditions, conventions and life of the British and Uzbek. Maxims and proverbs are the foremost profitable treasury of the

otherworldly culture of the individuals, its mind and creative power are concluded in them. The think about of proverbs makes it conceivable to memorize the British and Uzbek on the other hand, instead of displayed in broad generalizations and judgments around this country, permits you to open the little-known highlights of the English personality and Uzbek personality such as, for illustration, tirelessness, tirelessness, riskiness. Oral borrowings due to personal contacts are assimilated more completely and more rapidly than literary borrowings through the written speech. In the end of my course paper work I can say I have learned many kind of proverbs and sayings in Uzbek and British culture and people of this notions used it properly in speech etiquette. As well as I understand that using saying and proverbs makes our speech more politely, effectively and under stable to the locutor.

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